

INTERFACE ENGINEERING IN SOME OXIDE/OXIDE COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

Two oxide fiber/oxide matrix composite systems, alumina type fiber/glass matrix and mullite type fiber/mullite matrix, were prepared. The interfaces in these composites were engineered using SnO_2 coating on alumina fibers and BN or BN/SiC coatings on mullite fibers, such that deformation mechanisms conducive to toughness enhancement could be brought to play. Significant improvements in the mechanical properties of these oxide/oxide composites could be achieved by incorporation of these interfacial coatings.

Keywords: Composites, Oxides, Interface, Fiber coatings

1. INTRODUCTION

Ceramic matrix composites (CMCs) capable of maintaining excellent strength and fracture toughness are required for high temperature structural applications. Many of these applications require exposure to an oxidizing environment, as such the thermodynamic stability and oxidation resistance of CMCs become important issues. Nonoxide fiber/nonoxide matrix composites, such as C/C, SiC/SiC, and SiC/Si₃N₄, generally show good low temperature strength, but oxidation resistance is a major limitation (1, 2). Nonoxide fiber/oxide matrix composites or oxide fiber/nonoxide matrix composites, e.g., C/glass, SiC/glass, SiC/alumina, SiC/mullite, and Al₂O₃/SiC, do not have high oxidation resistance because the permeability constant for the diffusion of oxygen is high, resulting in rapid oxygen permeation through the oxide matrix (3-5). It would thus appear that in applications where stability in air at high temperature is a prime objective, oxide fiber/oxide matrix composites should be considered because they are inherently stable in air.

Some oxide/oxide matrix composite systems have been investigated (e.g., see Ref.6-9). A strong fiber/matrix bond forms in the oxide matrices reinforced with uncoated oxide fibers, such as in the like/like systems (e.g., mullite/mullite) (6,7) or in the mixed systems (e.g., Al₂O₃/SiO₂) (8,9) where compound(s) forms at the interface, and the overall mechanical properties of those composites were not much improved. As a consequence, a barrier layer needs to be introduced to prevent chemical interaction between the fiber and matrix, and thus, prevent strong interfacial chemical bonding. The objectives of this work were to use an interface engineering approach, involving fiber coating, microstructure characterization of the interface, thermal stress analysis, mechanical test and

fractography study, into an alumina type fiber/silica-based glass as well as mullite/mullite systems to weaken the interfacial bond in order to achieve the oxide/oxide composites with high work of fracture and a noncatastrophic failure mode.

2. MATERIALS AND EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

Two kinds of alumina fibers were used in a borosilicate glass, N51A, matrix composites. PRD-166 fiber manufactured by Du Pont, Inc., Wilmington, DE, is an α -alumina based fiber containing 15-20 wt% yttria stabilized tetragonal zirconia particle. Single crystal alumina fiber, Saphikon manufactured by Saphikon, Inc., Milford, NH, was also used. Nextel 480 and Nextel 550 fibers manufactured by 3M Co., St Paul, MN, were used in mullite matrix composites. Nextel 480 is a polycrystalline fiber with an essentially mullite composition. The as-received Nextel 550 is not crystalline mullite but a mixture of δ -alumina and amorphous silica with mullite composition, which can be transformed to mullite when heated above 1200 °C (10). Mullite powder synthesized via a diphasic gel route in our laboratory was used as matrix with Nextel 480 and 550 fibers. The fiber coatings, SnO₂ for PRD-166 and Saphikon fibers, were applied by chemical vapor deposition in our laboratory, while BN and BN/SiC for Nextel 480 and Nextel 550 were applied via CVD by 3M Co., respectively. In the double coating, the outer layer was SiC. All the composites with coated and uncoated fibers were fabricated by slurry impregnation method (11). Consolidation of composites was done by hot-pressing. The details of the fabrication have been reported elsewhere (12).

Optical and scanning electron microscopes were used for general characterization of the microstructure of the composites. Secondary ion mass spectrometry (SIMS) was used to identify the coatings in composites. Bend strength of composites was measured in three-point bend tests at room temperature using rectangular bar-shaped specimens with fiber direction parallel to the length of the specimen. The work of fracture (WOF) and the critical stress intensity factor of the composites were measured at room temperature using Chevron-notched bar specimen in three-point bend test.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Characterization of the interface

A detailed metallographic investigation of the tin dioxide interphase produced at different temperatures and different times was made (13). Results of the SIMS characterization of the PRD-166 fiber/SnO₂/glass composite, shown in Fig. 1, indicated that the Sn⁺ in the coating was localized to the coating only. This was shown earlier by electron microprobe work also (14).

Figure 2(a) shows the cross section of the 1 μ m BN coated Nextel 480 fiber. SIMS showed that the layer on the periphery of the fibers was BN, see Fig. 2(b). The microstructure of the BN/SiC coated Nextel 550 fiber, Fig. 3(a), shows that the fiber was fairly uniformly coated with two layers, BN and SiC, with thickness of about 0.1 μ m and 0.2 μ m, respectively. SIMS confirmed the presence of the double coating in the composites, as shown in Fig. 3(b,c). Thicker BN coating was used to survive the processing conditions in order to provide a desired weak interface. By the same token, the outer SiC coating was used to protect the BN inner layer from oxidation during composite fabrication, which is well known to have excellent resistance to high temperature oxidation owing to the formation of a protective film of silica on the surface.

3.2 Thermal stress analysis

Thermal stresses are generated in composite materials because of thermal expansion coefficient mismatch between the matrix and reinforcement, the

importance of which is well recognized. The thermal stresses in coated and uncoated PRD-166/glass as well as Saphikon/glass were evaluated using two- and three-element models (15). The results showed a radial tensile stress component at fiber/coating and coating matrix interfaces. This is desirable in order to weaken the interfacial bonding. In the mullite/mullite composite, the thermal expansion coefficient match between the composite components can eliminate the risk of the possible damage caused by thermal stresses. Thermal stresses induced by BN coating were analyzed (16). It showed a tensile radial stress less than 10 MPa at the fiber/coating interface, which was also favorable for the weak interface.

3.3 Mechanical properties

The three-point bend strength, work of fracture, and critical stress intensity factors determined for PRD-166/glass and mullite/mullite composites are listed in Table 1. As can be seen, significant improvements specially in fracture toughness were attained with the interface engineered alumina/glass and mullite/mullite composites. Toughness values between 6 and 11.6 MPa.m^{1/2} were obtained in mullite/mullite composites.

The composite with 1 μm BN-coated Nextel 480 exhibited damage tolerant characteristics with a load-bearing capacity even beyond the maximum load, as indicated by a gradual load drop which continued up to a significant amount of displacement without complete failure during the test, as seen in Fig. 4. After heat treatment leading to complete mullite crystallization of the matrix, this composite still showed non-catastrophic failure, also shown in Fig. 4. The loss of fiber strength resulted from the heat treatment was responsible for the load drop to a certain level after heat treatment. Similar to the case of Nextel 480/BN/mullite composites, the composites of Nextel 550/BN/SiC/mullite showed non-brittle failure, see Fig. 5.

3.4 Fracture characteristics of composites

3.4.1 Alumina/glass system

Scanning electron micrographs of the fracture surfaces obtained in three-point bend test of the various composites, with coated and uncoated, are shown in Figs. 6 and 7. In the case of PRD-166/glass and Saphikon/glass composites, the bonding between the uncoated fiber and the matrix were very strong, and brittle, flat fracture resulted. Introduction of the SnO₂ fiber coating results in a weakening of the fiber/matrix interface. As a result the fracture observed in the case of the coated fiber composites exhibited a relatively non-planar fracture, see Fig. 6(b). The lack of extensive fiber pullout in PRD-166/SnO₂/glass was attributed to the radial clamping due to the surface roughness of the PRD-166 fiber (17). Comparison of the effects of interfacial roughness and thermal stress on the radial stress at the interface, using a model proposed by Kerans et al.(18), showed that the effect of roughness induced radial compressive strain was an order of magnitude greater than the tensile thermal strain in this system (15). Therefore, the surface texture of the fiber can have a pronounced effect on the debonding and pullout characteristics of the composites. This was demonstrated by incorporating relatively smooth single alumina fibers (Saphikon) into the same glass matrix. Bend tests carried out on this composite exhibited extensive fiber/matrix debonding and fiber pullout, see Fig. 7(b). The important point to note here is that pullout occurred at the fiber/coating interface. This is expected because SnO₂ and alumina have no mutual solid solubility.

3.4.2 Mullite/mullite system

Scanning electron micrographs of the fracture surfaces obtained in three-point bend test of the mullite/mullite composites are shown in Figs. 8 & 9. The coating in Nextel 480/mullite was found on the pulled-out fiber surface with some peeling-off or separation from the fiber, see Fig. 8. This indicates that both the interfaces of matrix/coating and coating/fiber were weakly bonded. The

pulled-out fiber surfaces in Nextel 550/mullite composite were mostly clean and smooth, see Fig. 9. This indicates that, unlike Nextel 480/BN/mullite in which the fiber pullout could occur at the interfaces of either matrix/coating or coating/fiber, the fiber pullout occurred along the interface of the fiber and coating only.

4. CONCLUSIONS

The fiber/matrix interaction in oxide/oxide composites can be effectively controlled by interface engineering approach. Tin dioxide, BN, and BN/SiC would appear to be effective coating materials for the oxide/oxide composite systems investigated in this work. Incorporation of fiber coatings such as SnO₂ coating, BN coating, and SiC/BN double coating, together with other considerations, such as thermal stress, surface roughness of the fiber, and composite processing parameters, allowed us to make oxide/oxide composites showing high work of fracture and a noncatastrophic failure mode.

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Table 1. Mechanical properties of the composites

Composites	V_f	σ_{max} (MPa)	WOF (J/m ²)	K_{Ic} (MPa m ^{1/2})
PRD-166/glass				
Uncoated	0.40	225	750	2.5
SnO ₂ -Coated	0.35	150	920	3.3
Nextel 480/mullite				
Uncoated	0.45	104	56	1.8
As-HP	0.45	106	47	1.9
BN-coated	0.41	322	2410	11.6
As-HP	0.41	258	1630	8.5
HT				
Nextel 550/mullite				
Uncoated	0.47	87	18	1.5
As-HP	0.47	71	12	1.4
HT				
SiC/BN-coated	0.33	182	733	7.1
As-HP	0.33	223	308	6.0
HT				

As-HP : as hot pressed; HT : after heat treatment.

Fig. 1. (a) Secondary electron image of a PRD-166/SnO₂/glass composite, (b) Sn⁺ mapping by SIMS in a SnO₂-coated PRD-166/glass composite.

Fig. 2. (a) Cross section of a BN-coated Nextel 480 fiber, showing the coating thickness $\sim 1 \mu\text{m}$, (b) B^+ mapping by SIMS in a BN-coated Nextel 480/mullite composite.

Fig. 3. (a) Cross section of a SiC/BN coated Nextel 550 fiber, showing the double coating, (b, c) SIMS analysis of the surface of a SiC/BN-coated Nextel 550/mullite composite, showing the presence of boron and silicon.

Fig. 4. Load-displacement curves obtained in Chevron-notch tests for Nextel 480/mullite composites in as hot-pressed and heat-treated conditions.

Fig. 5. Load-displacement curves of obtained in Chevron-notch tests for Nextel 550/mullite composites in as hot-pressed and heat-treated conditions.

Fig. 6. Fracture surface of PRD-166/SnO₂/glass composite, showing the crack deflection and partial fiber pullout.

Fig. 7. Fracture surface of Saphikon/SnO₂/glass composite, showing the neat fiber pullout.

Fig. 8. Fracture surface of BN-coated Nextel 480/mullite composites, (a) hot-pressed and (b) hot-pressed and heat-treated.

Fig. 9. Fracture surface of SiC/BN-coated Nextel 550/mullite composites, (a) hot-pressed and (b) hot-pressed and heat-treated.